

Effects of schools Classroom management on learners' academic performance in four selected Primary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract: The study aimed at investigating the effects of classroom management on learners' academic performance in primary schools and the study sought to investigate the classroom management styles, classroom activities, teacher-pupil engagement and curriculum implementation in schools. The study employed a mixed paradigm and descriptive survey design that sampled four schools, Head teachers, teachers and learners. Data was obtained from respondents by means of interviews, questionnaires and classroom observation schedules. Frequency, percentages, tables, graphs and pie-charts were used to analyze the quantitative and qualitative data obtained. Data was then analyzed manually in some cases and also, a combination of software MS Access and MS Excel. The findings revealed that classroom management has effects on learners' academic performance and achievement in literacy and the study recommended that the school administrators should ensure that teachers' supervisions and monitoring are done and teachers should employ good classroom management skills, teaching strategizing and pupil involvement in classroom activities.

Keywords: Affective, Curriculum, Dominant, Interpersonal.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning is measured through learning objectives or behavioural objectives also known as functional or performance objectives. These contain action verbs that are testable. When the teacher teaches, he or she expects to get some evidence of his or her teaching through the performance of learners. The performance is reflected in what learners do as they carry out activities indicated in the learning objectives. A good teacher, according to The World Book Encyclopedia, T, Volume 17 (1960:55) provides guidance for the learner. This guidance encourages the learner to do things that result in desired learning such as the ability to read and write. Learning is an activity of the learner. Teaching creates conditions that will encourage and stimulate learning.

According to Watson *et al.*, (2007) in Muijs and Reynolds (2011:102) "classroom management is crucially linked to preparation." In one study of effective teachers, for example, they were found to strongly emphasize effective planning and organization as prerequisites for effective teaching, not least, as good planning facilitates classroom management...

Generally, the teacher deals with a group of children who should all do what is planned or reflected in lesson objective. This is not easy because each child should be catered for. The complication is apparent when we consider individual differences. Dean (1992:9) points out that "education at school is about children learning." Children are different from one another and are likely to respond differently to different approaches and treatment. Any group of children, however,

homogeneous, is a collection of very different individuals. It is not really possible or efficient for children to be taught individually but they do need some individual attention.

Classroom management is a crucial part of the teaching process. This is an area where teaching can be branded as useless or helpful because of the manner in which classes or individual learners are handled. This is about what goes on as the teacher administers a lesson. For example, children should be in a safe and favourable environment; they should enjoy the classroom atmosphere; feeling free and at ease with each other and their teacher. Research shows that children learn more effectively when the atmosphere is appreciably favourable. (Bennet and Wood, 1999) in (Muijs and Reynolds, 2011) state that research has shown that young children learn best when they are actively interacting with others and their environment rather than being passive recipients of information.

Communication is another potent factor in teaching, and teaching entirely depends on it. This is why some scholars state that teaching and communication are inseparable. (Nacino-Brown *et al.*, 1982:21) explain that, "effective teaching implies effective communication. Hence there can be no separation of the goal to improve teaching and the goal to communication."

1.1 Statement of the problem

When the teacher teaches, he or she is expected to deal with any event or misbehaviour that is likely to disrupt teaching and learning. This means that class room managerial skills are used to ensure that the classroom atmosphere is conducive enough to foster both teaching and learning (MOE, 2013) Challenges such as learners making noise, moving about unnecessarily or doing anything to make learners fail to concentrate on learning activities can lead to poor performance on the part of learners.

1.2 Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of classroom management on learners' academic performance in four selected primary schools in Lusaka Province.

1.3 Research objectives

1. To assess the effects of classroom management on teaching and learning.
2. To establish factors that affect classroom teaching and learning.
3. To highlight the correlation between classroom management and academic performance.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by Fiedler's Contingency Theory of leader effectiveness, Fiedler (1958) which claims that to lead an organization, the optimal course of action is contingent or dependent upon the internal and external situation and the theory focuses on how situational variables interact with leader personality and behaviour. Fiedler believed that leadership style is a reflection of personality (trait-theory orientated) as well as behaviour (behavioural-theory orientated), and that leadership skills like styles are basically constant. Leaders do not change skills and styles, they change the situation. The contingency leadership model is used to determine whether a person's leadership style is task or relationship orientated, and if the situation matches the leader's style to maximise performance (Kendra, 2019). Contingency theories of leadership focus on particular variables related to the environment that might determine which particular style of leadership is best suited for the situation. According to this theory, no leadership style is best in all situations. Truly effective leadership is not just about the qualities of the leader, it is about striking the right balance between behaviours, needs, and context. Good leaders are able to assess the needs of their followers, take stock of the situation, and then adjust their behaviours accordingly. Success depends on a number of variables including the leadership style, qualities of the followers and aspects of the situation.

1.5 Significance of the Study

It is hoped that the findings of the study would contribute to the knowledge gap amongst all the stake holders interested in education management and learners' classroom achievement as class room managerial skills would be used to ensure that the classroom atmosphere is conducive enough to foster both teaching and learning as well as modify the educational system and make it more relevant and responsive to national needs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The classroom teacher

The teacher is expected to be resourceful enough to make lessons meaningful and relevant; the idea that life is full of problems and that the ability to deal with them successfully is desirable. Creativity has been rated as one of the most important factors in classroom management; motivation is the life-blood of any human activity. The teacher's preparation and planning are crucial. Equally crucial is the question of subject knowledge. The teacher who is not well-versed in the subjects he or she teaches is more likely to create managerial problems. Another facet of classroom management is classroom climate. Pupils work better under favourable classroom atmosphere. Classroom climate is quite a wide-ranging concept encompassing the mood or atmosphere that is created in the teacher's classroom through the rules set out, the way the teacher interacts with pupils and the physical environment is set out (Greeners and Reezigt, 1999). Communication is crucial to classroom management. It is through it that teaching takes place. Without it there would be no learning. This is simply because it is through this process that human beings exchange ideas, information, skills, attitudes and knowledge. Without communication, no progress or development would take root. (Best and Kahn, 2006) attribute success in communication to the complexity nature of the human brain. According to them it has enabled them to develop sounds and symbols, letters and numbers that make communication possible.

According to (Wragg, 1993) without the ability to manage the class effectively, any other skills teachers have may be neutralized. It is not good knowing one's subject matter, being able to devise interesting activities appropriate to the topic, knowing what sort of questions to ask or being able to give a clear explanation, if one cannot obtain a hearing or organize a group of children.

2.2 Teaching and learning

Teaching and learning are activities created by societies to offer education through a host of strategies or provisions such as curriculum. The aims of education are actualized through the performance on the part of learners. Education as a social institution operates through a number of agencies, and some of these are schools. These are places of teaching and learning. Generally speaking, schools offer knowledge, skills and attitudes to enable learners fit in their society. After all, every society is made up of members whose role is to support the very society. According to (Meighan and Blatchford, 2003) a structural functionalist view of education tends to stress the activity of schools in training and selecting children so that they fit into some necessary slot in a relatively harmonious society. This view implies that children need to be manipulated in some way for that society's convenience, or for some other reason. The teacher is said to be like a potter moulding clay or like gardener cultivating plants, or a builder building a house on sound foundations.

2.3 Classroom management

Classroom management is fundamentally associated with several forces encompassing all areas of classroom life, and the teacher should be busy doing all he or she can to create an optimum atmosphere for learning. Since learning is based on evidence drawn from accomplished learning activities, the teacher is expected to ensure that learning activities done by each learner. In other words, learning outcomes are intimately connected to the learner's participation in tasks and the economical use of time. According to (Muijs and Reynolds, 2011) one of the main features to emerge from teacher effectiveness research as a correlation of pupil achievement and attainment is the *opportunity to learn*. This refers to whether or not the content tested for (on whatever test is used to measure pupils' achievement) has actually been seen by the pupils during the course of the year. The main factors to influence opportunity to learn are curriculum coverage (the extent to which the content covered by the teacher actually matches the content covered by the test) and the related factor of how many hours are actually penciled in to study the subject tested. However, another major factor influencing opportunity to learn within the lesson is *time on task* that is the amount of time within a lesson that pupils spend engaging with the curriculum rather than on other activities such as socializing, moving around the classroom and being disciplined.

Classroom management can be characterized by the strategies that the teacher undertakes to deal with classroom environment, classroom climate and learner behaviour. Under classroom environment, the teacher is more likely to concentrate on the physical nature of the place where learners are deployed. This place, in all cases, is expected to be safe, comfortable and stimulating. In all likelihood, learning takes place in a place and between and among things. According to Stones (1966:17) "when an organism learns it adapts its behaviour to cope with changes in its environment."

In the classroom, there are things from which to make concepts. It is important that things real and abstract are used, deployed in ways that promote concept formation. Concepts according to Feldman (1996:257) “are categorizations of objects, events and people that share common properties.” By employing concepts, we are able to organize the complex phenomena into simpler, and therefore more easily usable cognitive categories. Classroom management is basically about maintaining favourable or conducive environment for learning.

2.4 Classroom activities

Classroom activities such as reading writing and speaking are typical of daily school life. Extra mural activities are also encouraged: children go out to perform shows to do with speaking spelling acting and so forth. Any such activities are educative and are consistently carried out because they foster learning, and consequently boost the academic performance. Routines, rules and procedures also shape the behaviour of learner activities. Learners learn to appreciate the time they spend in what they are told to do. They learn to avoid wasting time for they are required to get engaged in activities which are basically deemed to be unfruitful in terms of academic performance. Nevertheless, teachers are expected to deal with their work in a serious manner since their job is very crucial to human development.

2.5 Pupil achievement

The pupil comes to school to learn what is socially and economically acceptable. The teacher engages learners in teaching and the learner is expected to speak, read, write and listen or comprehend. These activities can be assessed or evaluated to establish the level of competence or performance on the part of the learner. When the learner is not given an opportunity to learn, nothing can be achieved After all, learning is about doing something through skills acquisition and knowledge that can be measured.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. Exploratory and descriptive designs were as well considered appropriate as they also allowed for more flexible strategies of data collection in order to answer the research questions, (Best and Kahn, 2006). Further, (Kerlinger in Kombo and Trump, 2006) points out that a descriptive study may often result in the formation of important principles of knowledge and solutions to significant problems. By incorporating both qualitative and quantitative aspects of research, the study aimed at collecting information from respondents on the effects of classroom management on learners’ academic performance in Primary schools, highlight factors affecting classroom management, curriculum implementation and teacher-pupils engagement in classroom activities.

3.2 Research sites

This study was under taken from the four selected schools in Mwense District namely Kabana Primary, Kabungo Primary, Mulungu Primary and Bulongo Primary School. The research sites are basically in highly densely populated, unplanned settlements and people rely on odd jobs for their livelihoods.

3.3 Population, Sample and Sapling Procedure

The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the four selected Primary schools and the District education office. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select Head teachers and an Education Standards Officer while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the learners and teachers, (Agesa,2012). The sample size comprised of 90 respondents. Also, the primary data was complimented by the secondary data which was derived from government policy documents, ministerial reports and relevant literature on the teaching and learning of initial literacy. Structured open-ended interviews were conducted and questionnaires and observation schedules were used to respondents. The internet also supplemented data for the study.

In the sampling of institutions, the study adopted the stratified cluster random sampling technique. Sampling was done zone by zone. Schools were clustered by zones. One zone was purposively selected based on highest number of schools. The sampling was done at three levels: Sampling zones and schools- level 1, Sampling learners-level 2, Sampling Head teachers and teachers -level 3.

3.4 Data Analysis

In this study, data was analysed qualitatively as the semi structured interviews and questionnaires were used as data collection instruments. Thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the semi structured interviews and questionnaires (Smith, 2013). Frequency, percentages, tables, pie-harts and graphs were used to analyse data. The data gathered was analysed according to the themes of the study, the order of the research objectives and questions. The research collected data through in-depth interviews, classroom observations and questionnaires. Qualitative data collected was analysed using thematic analysis while quantitative data collected was analysed through the use of Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for generation of tables, graphs, pie charts, percentages and frequencies.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The researcher got permission from Debs and school authorities and consents, assents from respondents who were involved in the research. The research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents and the researcher was fully conscious of the need to abide by the ethical rule of respecting the privacy of individuals taking part in the research. In the same way, all the respondents of the research were to remain unidentified to the public as all their valuable views, opinions as well as their identities will forever remain hidden.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings were presented according to set research objectives:

4.1 Classroom management

As illustrated in Table 1 below, survey results indicate an array of activities with teacher personality having the highest score of 82.8% followed by teacher-pupil engagement (79.7%) and learner organisation (70.3%). Class activities with the least scores were teacher resourcefulness (20.2%), working on group projects (23.7%) and playing learning games at 31.3%.

Table 1: Teacher performance in classroom activities

Description of class activity	Observed or not observed		TOTAL
	Observed	Not observed	
Teacher personality	82.8%	17.2%	100%
Classroom organization	69.6%	30.4%	100%
Teacher resourcefulness	20.2%	79.8%	100%
Teacher communication	43.25	56.8%	100%
Learner practical exercises	66.2%	33.8%	100%
Teacher pupil engagement	79.7%	20.3%	100%
Learners' books	50.4%	49.6%	100%
Learners organization	70.3%	29.7%	100%
Learners working on group projects	23.7%	76.3%	100%
Learners playing academicgames Sketches or teacher organized learning	31.3%	68.7%	100%

Source: Research findings 2020

One of very useful exercise for both teachers and student-teachers is to set class management firmly into the context of reflection and action across the whole repertoire of teaching skills. On its own, the ability to manage people resources, time or space is meaningless. Only in a context will techniques and insights acquire value and meaning. This means that teachers develop, like the ability to explain new concepts clearly, to ask different kinds of questions or to listen attentively to what children are saying (Wragg, 1993).

The teacher is expected to know a great deal about teaching effectively. This is because teaching involves a host of things: subject knowledge, timing of learning activities, motivating learners and providing techniques to improve memory among other things.

Learners learn more when they are given opportunities to practice. It is through practice that learners learn. The teacher is expected to create chances for learners to repeatedly do one thing. This is important because rehearsals and practice are of

memory and other faculty of learning. (Feldman, 1980: 249) states that although practice does not necessarily make perfect, it does help. By studying and rehearsing material past the point of initial mastery—a process called overlearning—people are able to show better long-term recall than if they stop practicing after their initial learning of the material.

Effective classroom management entails presenting the same material over and over without inducing monotony. The idea is simply to provide ample practice so that the material presented is effectively mastered. (Thompson, 1975:5) states that “frequently we fail to teach a skill because we haven’t provided instructional dosage.” Using your back of successful teaching ideas you will be able to quickly prescribe appropriate instruction to meet your students’ learning needs with highly motivating activities. Then, you will be able to present independent learning experiences for certain students while providing corrective instruction for those in need. Providing you with such versatility is [important].

Learning activities that take place in lessons need practice. It is out of practice that learning takes place. According to The World Book Encyclopedia, L, Volume 12 (1993:162) “learning is an important field of study in psychology”. Psychology define learning as the process by which changes in behaviour results from experience or practice.

4.2 Learner academic performance

Table 2 below illustrates the action teachers take to help pupils in class having difficulties in a classroom teaching and learning session as regards their academic performance during.

Table 2: Distribution of teachers by actions taken to help learner having difficulties

	Teacher’s action	Response		Percentage of cases
		Actual	Percentage	
Teacher Helping pupils having difficulties	Work on one-on-one with learners	04	66.7%	20.0%
	Give extra assignments	05	83.3%	25.0%
	Pair with a good learner	02	33.3%	10.0%
	Find someone to work with or tutor the learner	02	33.3%	10.0%
	Recommend outside tutoring	03	50.0%	15.0%
	Talk to parents or guardians	01	16.7%	5.0%
	Report Head teacher	02	33.3%	10.0%
	Take no action	01	16.7%	10.0%

Source: Research findings 2020

According to the teachers, the solutions for the learners having trouble with their academic performance during a teaching and learning session lay in giving them extra assignments (83.3%), work with learners on one-on-one (66.7%) and option number three was to pair them with a good learner (33.3%).

4.3 Teaching, learning and school management

On pedagogical leadership, almost all Head teachers (99.5%) agreed that it is their responsibility to help teachers teach better in schools and they pointed out that three most important duties of Head teachers were; ensure quality teaching (41.5%), ensure children learning (35.9%) and ensure availability of materials (23%). With regard to leadership style, many Head teachers exercise pedagogical leadership by communicating often with teachers (24.1%), encourage team work among teachers (23.9%) and share Head teacher’s knowledge and vision with teachers (19.4%).The top three strategies on how Head teachers assess quality of teaching were classroom observation (29.6%) learners’ marks or test results (23.3%) and teachers’ performance reviews at 16.2%. This result was consistent with those on how Head teachers identifies teachers that need help, with classroom observation ranking top followed by teacher performance reviews and then learners marks. Similarly, if a teacher has a problem, a Head teacher mostly discusses the problem area in teacher group meetings (23.8%), observes teacher’s class (20%) and sometimes pairs them with a good teacher (16.5%).

Survey findings show that all the teachers (100%) are never monitored by peers, (83.3%) never monitor themselves, and no teacher (0%) is ever monitored internally while (16.7%) teachers are never monitored externally. Weekly monitoring is only at 16.7% internally. Not all teachers (83.3%) are monitored annually. Internal monitoring of teachers has more scores than any other type of monitoring. On internal monitoring,

Source: Research findings 2020

Figure 1: Teacher monitoring

Teacher meetings and classroom observations were cited as common ways of discussing and resolving challenges associated with learning and teaching in schools. For example, 29.7% of Head teachers said they organized discussion meetings for teachers in each academic year and on average, a Head teacher observes a classroom teacher 5 times in one academic year. However, when asked for proof of notes or other documentation during observations, almost a quarter (18.8%) of Head teachers could not provide evidence. On feedback, the survey found that 60% of Head teachers provided one-to-one feedback with 30.9% through a written report and group discussion at 7.6%. Even though 98% of Head teachers said that teachers are required to prepare daily lesson plans, this practice is not the same when it comes to preparing individualized teacher improvement plans as only 47.2% indicated it is happening.

In a classroom we find the teacher and his or her learners. The teacher is the leader and ensures that what he or she says is done by his or her learners. Here is the picture to show the dominant position of the teacher (Wragg,1993). The teacher is an organizer of routines and rules, space, seating plans resources and time spent on both teaching and learning. The environment should be made unfavourable or favourable by things done to and in them. The teacher himself or herself was personally for the atmosphere under which learner learnt. This could be maintained through routines and rules. Communication is the source of kinds of development. (Kunczik, 1995:5) states that “teaching is a type of communication through learners are developed into educated beings.”

Resourcefulness is important in both teaching and learning and (Pollard et al, 2008:100) state that “materials are the bread-and-butter consumable of a school, such as paper pencils, creative and artistic materials.” The quality of learning of experiences will be directly affected by such provision. On creativity (Benjamin et al, 1990:283) state that “often creative thinking is viewed as a special case of problem solving.”

As regards organizational skills, effective teachers are able to organize their learners in ways that foster both teaching and learning. Poorly organized learners do little or nothing in terms of group and individual work. (Stevens, 1976:109) states that “the teacher must remember that the environment should develop as children interests emerge and are understood.” In other words, the environment should be dynamic not static. The arrangement of the learning areas and pictorial work of the teacher and children should be changed from time to time, for novelty is an important feature of learning.

4.4 Qualities of an effective teacher

Great teachers have several qualities that work together to enhance their teaching skills, knowledge and attitudes. As for skills, they show that they are able to do things correctly and smartly. Speaking, listening, reading and writing are some of the skills that they are good at. When speaking, for instance, they ensure that they are audible enough to be heard or listened to by their learners and they avoid using words which are too tough for their learners (Feldman,1980). In other words they are simple and clear. Furthermore they use all possible paralinguistic features to optimize communication.

Effective teachers are typically knowledgeable. They know what they teach. Knowing their subject matter makes those special because some teachers even teach subjects they do not really master. This is particularly true about primary school teachers. Quist (2000:2) states that “in most countries, the primary curriculum includes at least eight and sometimes as many as fourteen different subjects.” Many teachers are aware that they do not know enough about some of these subjects, as they did not study them at school or during their initial teacher training.

This shows that many teachers who have not been reading to improve their professional status, have not been able to master their subjects. The other virtue is alertness which Muijs and Reynolds (2011:118) state that an important skill that comes to some extent with experience is what Kounin (1970) referred to as “with-itness.” This is the ability to spot all misbehaviour quickly and accurately and identify the right pupil as the culprit. A teacher should be sensitive to learners’ different personalities and experiences. This is important because there are individual differences in learners. Dean (1992:9) states that “education at school is about children learning.” Other virtues are leadership, creativity, resourcefulness and stimulation.

4.5 Factors that affect teaching and learning

Teachers as professionals, have diverse way of thinking about the nature of teaching and learning and the idea that the teacher values and perceptions in reference to teaching and learning play a practical part in the way he or she handles his or her own class. Teaching is dependent on many factors some of which personal values and perceptions concerning on how best teaching can be administered (Quist,2000). While we appreciate the fact that rote learning is not compatible with the generally acceptable ways of learning, it has proved useful to many people who were taught who did not believe in human rights, democracy in learning and humanistic overtones. In this case, it is not surprising that beating was allowed if it produced desirable results. Memorization was a potent tool through which learning took place. Learners memorized and later understood what they had memorized.

Today, some teachers use some mechanical technical techniques and strategies of making learning take place. Committing the multiplication table to memory and drilling learners to master sentence structures and parts of speech, and punishing learners to do repetitive exercises such as copying a long text several times exemplify learning that takes place because of the teacher’s effort. According to (Feldman, 1980:249) “although practice does not necessarily make perfect, it does help.” By studying and rehearsing material past the point of initial mastery- a process called over learning- people are able to show better long- term recall than if they stop practicing after their initial learning of material. It is important to identify situations when practice is necessary. Feldman (ibid) states that we benefit from our memory when the memorized material is retrieved. The retrieval is much easier when there are things to make us recall.

The mind or brain cannot sometimes work properly because of being tired. Many learners strain it when they cram- they learn many things and force them into memory. This is not effective. Feldman (ibid) argues that people who cram for tests should note that the best retention comes from practice that is distributed over many sessions, rather than left for one long session. Teaching as a science and art should be used to help out learners who are struggling to learn. This is particularly so when they fail to read and write. These two skills are basic ones and are a foundation. It is necessary for the teacher to devise ways and means of to ensure that all the learners with learning difficulties in any area are helped out. For example, (Medwel et al, 2009: 72) show that “shared reading is an important demonstration, not only of the mechanics of reading but also a chance to engage children with ways in which forms of writing achieve their purpose.”

4.6 Curriculum

According to (Quist, 2000:2) “in most countries, the primary curriculum includes at least eight and sometimes as many as fourteen different subjects.” Many teachers are aware that they do not know enough about some of these subjects, as they did not study them at school or during their initial teacher training. Because of this problem, she has proposed some ways of overcoming lack of subject knowledge. She has advised for example, reading the latest subject manuals issued by one’s government, borrow other peoples’ manuals for a while, visiting the local Teachers’ Resource Centre for materials, share knowledge with colleagues, the pupils’ parents or local experts and after learning from other people, it is important to practice what one learns. Quist (ibid: 3) states that “after the initial lesson preparation, give yourself time to rehearse as teachers are like actors.”

It is important to know a great deal about the subject one teaches. This is because failure to do so can lead learners to having no confidence in the teacher (Nacino-Brown et al,1982). When this happens the learner is more predisposed to misbehaviour. They can come about by showing no respect for the teacher. In this case, lack of respect for the teacher will breed all sorts of misbehaviour such as failing to do what the teacher asks the class to do.

When the teacher is knowledgeable, the class is inspired and motivated. The learners feel placed in the right hands. The learners are convinced that what they came to school for will be achieved. It is always important to realize that children come to school to learn what their parents or societies expect to be learnt from.

For the sake of clarity, a curriculum is examined from several levels. (Wallace, 1992:66) "curriculum is the content and specifications of a course or programme of study" (as in 'the history curriculum') or in a wider sense, the totality of the specified learning opportunities available in one education institution (as in 'the school curriculum') or, in its very widest sense, the programme of learning applying to all pupils in the nation (as in 'the national curriculum')

5. CONCLUSION

Teachers intend to get learners engaged in learning activities. Out of these activities, learners are able to generate experiences that lead to learning. This is not possible if learners cannot be made to that classroom managed is deemed to be instrumental in making learning feasible. As learners do what is stated in behavioural objectives, they are assessed and therefore are graded according to their performance. The marks that they get determine their academic performance status. Learners and their teachers do what they can to implement viable classroom management practices. Essentially classroom management is what teachers do to ensure that their learners are doing what is stated in the lesson objective. Classroom management is an integral part of professionalism. The teacher is expected to master rudiments of this important facet of teaching. It is through component that teaching maximizes opportunities for learning on the part of learners. It is important to appreciate the instrumental role of classroom management in fostering both teaching and learning. Learning is like buying and teaching is like selling. By this analogy it is clear that teaching takes places when learners learn. A lesson is not taught until it is learnt (Farrant, 1980:168). Teacher who practice effective classroom management teaches effectively and their learners consequently learn effectively. In classroom management we see the qualities and activities from the teachers. Effective managers of classes, have some qualities in them that make the great and successful teachers. Furthermore, they do things to bring about learning.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study were based on the conclusions and were as follows:

1. Teachers should master the rudiments of classroom management.
2. Teachers-learner engagement in classroom management should be enhanced.
3. Teachers and learners should implement viable classroom management.
4. Head teachers should master rudiments of pedagogical leadership.

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